

**PERCEPTIONS AND BARRIERS TO ICT INTEGRATION FOR
LANGUAGE LEARNING AND TEACHING IN EFL CLASSROOM**

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The progress in education brings about rapid changes, integrating the use of Information and Communication Technology (hence, ICT) in Indonesia. After completing the 2013 Curriculum revision process at the end of 2015 by the Ministry of Education and Culture, all primary and secondary schools must prepare themselves to implement 2013. According to Regulation of Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia No. 160 of 2014, the 2013 Curriculum is implemented in stages until the 2019/2020 academic year. In the attachment to Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 103 of 2014, related to the principles of learning (point 12), it stated that to achieve quality has been designed to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of learning, learning activities need to use the principles of utilizing ICT. The acceptance of this decision makes Indonesian education integrate every learning with ICT to advance the quality of education in Indonesia, especially in English language teaching. ICT is one of the things that can access communication globally. ICT practices are supported by technology using projectors, LCDs, laptops, LED TVs, tablets, computers, the internet, and smartphones (Rodliyah, 2018). In the 21st century education integrating technology, students and teachers are engaged in previously impossible ways, enabling the creation of new teaching and learning activities, increasing achievement, and expanding interactions with local and global communities. Teachers and students no longer depend on books and stationery that burden them in the learning process. Significantly, integrating ICT in children in elementary schools is very much needed for students and teachers. As the use of technology for young learners prepares the students to get the benefits of the technology (Dettori, 2004), it gives positive impacts, supports, and enhances the students' learning process (Kozma, 2003; Shin et al., 2014; Sutherland et al., 2008) and bring the students to the real-life situations (Lowther et al., 2008). The system integrating ICT in the learning process will improve the quality of education for students in increasing motivation, facilitating the acquisition of basic skills, promoting investigation and exploration, and preparing individuals

for the impetus of the technological world (Hidayati, 2016). The integration of information and communication technology (ICT) in language learning and teaching has become increasingly important in the digital age. However, there are still perceptions and barriers that hinder its effective implementation in English as a foreign language (EFL) classrooms.

One of the main barriers to ICT integration is the lack of access to technology and technical support. Some schools or teachers may not have the necessary resources or training to effectively use technology in the classroom. This can result in a negative perception of ICT integration, where teachers may view it as an additional burden or distraction from traditional teaching methods.

Another barrier is the perceived difficulty of integrating technology into language learning activities. Teachers may feel overwhelmed by the variety of digital tools available and struggle to identify which ones are appropriate for their students' needs and abilities. Additionally, some teachers may lack the necessary skills and confidence to effectively use technology in the classroom.

There may also be cultural or institutional barriers to ICT integration, where traditional teaching methods are deeply ingrained and resistant to change. Some teachers may view technology as a threat to their authority or expertise, or may be hesitant to adopt new teaching methods that challenge their established practices.

To overcome these barriers, it is important to provide teachers with the necessary training and support to effectively integrate technology into language learning activities. This can include professional development opportunities, access to technical support, and guidance on selecting appropriate digital tools. Moreover, it is important to promote a positive perception of ICT integration by highlighting its benefits for language learning and teaching. This can include increased student engagement, improved language skills, and enhanced communication and collaboration with peers and native speakers.

Overall, effective ICT integration in EFL classrooms requires a shift in perceptions and attitudes towards technology, as well as a commitment to providing teachers with the necessary resources and support to successfully incorporate it into their teaching practices.

ICT integration in EFL classrooms can provide numerous benefits for language learning and teaching. However, there are still perceptions and barriers that hinder its effective implementation. Some of these barriers include a lack of access to technology and technical support, difficulty in integrating

technology into language learning activities, and cultural or institutional resistance to change.

To overcome these barriers, it is important to provide teachers with the necessary training and support to effectively integrate technology into their teaching practices. This can include professional development opportunities, access to technical support, and guidance on selecting appropriate digital tools. Promoting a positive perception of ICT integration is also crucial. Highlighting its benefits for language learning and teaching, such as increased student engagement and improved language skills, can help shift attitudes towards technology.

Overall, effective ICT integration in EFL classrooms requires a commitment to providing teachers with the necessary resources and support, as well as a willingness to embrace new teaching methods that enhance language learning and teaching.

Perceptions and barriers to ICT integration for language learning and teaching in EFL classrooms have been widely discussed in the literature. Some studies suggest that teachers may have negative attitudes towards technology due to a lack of confidence in their own technological skills or a fear of losing control over the classroom (Ertmer, 1999; Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010).

Other studies point to institutional and cultural barriers, such as a lack of funding for technology or a resistance to change in traditional teaching methods (Levy & Stockwell, 2006; Hubbard & Levy, 2006). Additionally, access to technology and technical support can be limited in certain contexts, particularly in developing countries or low-income schools (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010).

However, there is also evidence to suggest that effective ICT integration can have numerous benefits for language learning and teaching. For example, digital tools can provide opportunities for more personalized and interactive learning experiences, as well as increased student motivation and engagement (Chapelle & Jamieson, 2008; Levy & Stockwell, 2006). To overcome these barriers and promote effective ICT integration in EFL classrooms, some researchers suggest the need for a shift in teacher education and training. This includes providing teachers with the necessary technological skills and knowledge, as well as guidance on how to integrate technology into language learning activities (Chapelle & Jamieson, 2008; Hubbard & Levy, 2006).

Additionally, promoting a positive perception of technology and its benefits for language learning and teaching can help to overcome resistance to change and

encourage teachers to embrace new teaching methods (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). Overall, effective ICT integration requires a commitment to providing teachers with the necessary resources and support, as well as a willingness to embrace new teaching methods that enhance language learning and teaching.

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